

Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG emission estimates

Deliverable D1.4:

**Report on QC/QA procedures for gamma
and other nuclear measurements**

Document information

Project Acronym	NuClim
Project Title	Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG emission estimates
EC grant agreement No.	101166515
Project starting / end date	1st September 2024 – 31 August 2028
Work Package No.	1
Work Package Title	Nuclear and ancillary measurements
Deliverable No.	1.4
Deliverable Title	Report on QC/QA procedures for gamma and other nuclear measurements
Lead Beneficiary	PTB
Contractual Delivery Date	M12
Actual Delivery Date	M14
Type	
Dissemination level	
Authors	Rieke Schäfer, Jussi Paatero, Susana Barbosa, Stefan Röttger
To be cited as	
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Document status

Date	By	Description
01.09.2025	Rieke Schäfer	Initial structure
24.09.2025	Susana Barbossa	Added chapter on total gamma radiation
08.10.2025	Jussi Paatero	Added chapter on radon progeny monitor, spectral gamma radiation measurements, dose rate monitor measurements and laboratory measurements of ^7Be and ^{210}Pb
09.10.2025	Rieke Schäfer	Revision, glossary, summary
09.10.2025	Stefan Röttger	Revision

Project executive summary

Radon is a unique atmospheric tracer. High-quality direct and indirect measurements of radon concentration can advance climate science, radiation protection and nuclear surveillance. These observations will reduce uncertainty in baseline characterisation of European greenhouse gas (GHG) levels and assist in environmental studies. The EU-funded NuClim project aims to investigate the influence of terrestrial factors on air masses, measure pollution events and explore the impact of natural planktonic communities on GHG emissions. Additionally, it will analyse marine boundary layer clouds and aerosols, and study wet deposition and meteorological processes affecting ambient gamma dose rates for nuclear surveillance networks.

Deliverable executive summary

To ensure the quality of the data produced within the NuClim project, great care is taken during measurement set-up, the measurement campaign and the data processing. This document details the quality assurance and control measures taken to ensure high-quality measurements for gamma and other nuclear measurements. The main points are the set-up following best practices and manufacturer recommendations, calibrations as necessary and checking the quality of the measurement results.

Glossary

ARM	Atmospheric Radiation Measurement
BEGe	Broad energy germanium
ENA	Eastern North Atlantic
FMI	Finnish Meteorological Institute
GM	Geiger-Müller
HPGe	High-purity germanium
QA	Quality assessment
QC	Quality control

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1 Introduction

Quality control (QC) and quality assurance (QA) are important to ensure continued high-quality measurement results. This includes proper measurement set-up, regular checks and maintenance of the sensors but also data processing steps.

The QA process maintains “a satisfactory level of quality in a data set or data collection so that the data available to potential users are sufficiently reliable and complete and can be used with confidence” (*Guidelines on Surface Station Data Quality Control and Quality Assurance for Climate Applications*, 2021). QC is defined as “the inspection, analysis, and other relevant actions taken to provide control over what is being done, [...] so that a desirable level of quality is achieved and maintained.” (EEA & Eionet, n.d.). The QC process ensures that “errors in the data, or in the continuity of the data, are detected by checking the data to assess representativeness in time and space and internal consistency, and by flagging any potential errors or inconsistencies” (*Guidelines on Surface Station Data Quality Control and Quality Assurance for Climate Applications*, 2021).

This document presents the steps that are taken within NuClim to ensure the high quality of gamma radiation and other nuclear measurements (except for radon measurements which are covered in deliverable D1.2).

As part of NuClim, several gamma spectrometry and other nuclear measurements are taken:

- radon progeny monitor (beta particle counting of short-lived radon progeny collected onto glass-fibre filters),
- spectral (CeBr₂ and NaI(Tl)) gamma radiation measurements by an in-situ scintillation gamma spectrometer,
- dose rate monitor measurements, and
- filters from the radon progeny monitor are measured for ⁷Be with a high-purity germanium (HPGe) gamma spectrometer,
- filters from the radon progeny monitor are measured for ²¹⁰Pb with an alpha/beta analyser, and
- total (NaI(Tl)) gamma radiation measurements by a total gamma radiation counter.

The instruments and their set-up are described in detail in deliverable D1.1 (“Field campaign report”).

2 Radon progeny monitor

2.1 Measurement set-up

A radon progeny monitor was installed to the Finnish Meteorological Institute’s (FMI) measurement container at the Eastern North Atlantic (ENA) Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) facility at Graciosa (Azores) in May 2025. ²²²Rn is measured via its beta emitting short-lived progeny collected onto a glass-fibre filter. Sample air is drawn through a filter wrapped around a cylindrical frame. The beta activity accumulating onto the filter is continuously recorded by a cylindrical Geiger–Müller (GM) counter mounted coaxially inside the filter frame. The system comprises of two identical filter/GM tube assemblies. A 3-way valve, controlled by a measurement computer, guides the air flow

through either of the filter/GM tube assemblies in four-hour periods. The sample air flow rate is measured with a mass flow meter. The pulses from the GM counters are recorded, together with air flow data, by a data logger and stored into a measurement computer at one-minute intervals. ^{222}Rn activity concentration is calculated from the pulse and air flow data, assuming an equilibrium with ^{222}Rn and its daughter nuclides, using the formulas presented in Paatero et al. (1994).

2.2 Calibration and maintenance

The efficiency calibration of the radon progeny monitor has been achieved by parallel measurements of radon progeny using pseudo-coincidence counting (Mattsson et al., 1996). The instrument has participated in an intercomparison exercise with satisfactory results (Schmithüsen et al., 2017). The weekly maintenance consists of replacing the filters with clean ones. The exposed filters are mailed to the FMI's laboratory for the analysis of ^{210}Pb and ^7Be . No other maintenance is required except occasional adding of vacuum grease to o-ring seals of the filter/GM tube assemblies.

2.3 Data pre-processing

The one-minute data is transferred from the measurement computer to the FMI's data collection system. There it is plotted and visually checked for outliers, missing data points etc. Hourly medians are calculated from the 1-minute data to reduce the variation due to counting statistics Figure 1.

Fig

ure 1 An example of ^{222}Rn activity concentrations in the air 10 m above the ground at Graciosa.

The 1-minute values are presented with red dots and the hourly medians with blue lines. The higher values during late night and early morning can be attributed to local emissions of radon, which stay close to the ground due to stratification of the surface air.

2.4 Data quality control

All the one-minute raw data is transferred from the measurement computer to the FMI's data collection system. There it is plotted and visually checked for outliers, missing data points etc. An example of the raw data is presented in Figure 2. The air flow readings confirm the proper working of the pump connected to the sample air line. The characteristic 4-hour variation of the GM tube count rates verifies the proper operation of the GM tubes. When the sample air is flowing through a filter, the count rate of the corresponding GM tube increases as beta activity gathers onto the filter. When the 3-way valve directs the air flow through the other filter assembly, the count rate begins decreasing exponentially with a half-time of about half an hour as the activity on the filter decays. The count rate returns approximately to the base line during the four-hour period due to the practically complete decay of short-lived ^{222}Rn progeny.

Figure 2 An example of 1-minute GM tube count rate and air flow data during a 24-hour period at Graciosa.

3 Spectral gamma radiation measurements

3.1 Measurement set-up

An *in-situ* gamma spectrometer was installed to the FMI's measurement container at the ENA ARM facility in May 2025. The spectrometer measures the energy spectrum of ambient gamma radiation within the energy range of about 50-3000 keV. The detector of the spectrometer is a 76 mm x 76 mm NaI(Tl) scintillation detector. Gamma spectra are recorded with one-hour intervals.

3.2 Calibration and maintenance

The energy calibration of the spectrometer was made before the measurement campaign started. The only maintenance needed is an occasional restart of the spectrometer program in the measurement computer. If a significant shift in the spectrum should occur, the amplification of the spectrometer can be adjusted from the linear amplifier.

3.3 Data pre-processing

The one-hour gamma spectrum data is transferred from the measurement computer to the FMI's data collection system for quality control and dissemination actions.

3.4 Data quality control

An example of a one-hour gamma spectrum measured at Graciosa is presented in Figure 3. The gathered 2048-channel spectra are plotted to check the general shape of the spectrum and the position of the potassium-40 gamma peak at the energy of 1460 keV.

Figure 3 The energy spectrum of ambient gamma radiation at Graciosa 24 May 2025, measurement time one hour.

4 Dose rate monitor measurements

4.1 Measurement set-up

A dose rate monitor (Rados/Mirion RD-02L) was installed to the FMI's measurement container at the ENA ARM facility in May 2025. External dose rate, mainly due to gamma radiation from the ground and cosmic radiation, is measured with the instrument having two halogen-quenched and energy-compensated GM tubes as detectors. The energy range of the instrument is 50-1300 keV for the dose rate range 0.01 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ -2000 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ and 80-1300 keV for the dose rate range 2 mSv/h-10000 mSv/h. The energy response is $\pm 30\%$ over the energy range 50-1300 keV from background to dose rate level of 10 mSv/h. The measured dose rate values are sent to the measurement computer in 10-minute intervals via an RS-232 serial line.

4.2 Calibration and maintenance

The instrument is factory calibrated, and the calibration interval covers the whole NuClim measurement period. The instrument requires no regular maintenance. The changes of data file names etc. can be done remotely from the FMI.

4.3 Data pre-processing

The 10-minute data is transferred from the measurement computer to the FMI's data collection system for quality control.

4.4 Data quality control

An example of the dose rate data is presented in Figure 4. Outliers clearly below the usual dose rate level are excluded from the data set. Outliers above the usual dose rate level are not excluded from the data set as these high values can be related to e.g. precipitation scavenging airborne radionuclides to the ground (Paatero & Hatakka, 1999).

Figure 4 Dose rate at Graciosa 15 June - 6 July 2025.

5 Laboratory measurements of ^7Be

5.1 Measurement set-up

The filters of the radon progeny monitor are changed once a week and sent to the FMI's laboratory. They are measured for ^7Be ($t_{1/2} = 53$ days) with HPGe spectrometry. The detector is a broad energy germanium (BEGe) detector with a relative efficiency of 50 %. The counting time varies from one to several days. ^7Be is assayed based on its 478 keV gamma emissions.

5.2 Calibration and maintenance

The energy calibration of the HPGe spectrometer is checked frequently by measuring ^{241}Am , ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co calibration sources. The efficiency calibration is traceable to international standards implemented in Finland by Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority (STUK).

5.3 Data pre-processing

The acquired 8096-channel gamma spectra are saved for later use. The net count rate of the 478 keV gamma peak and its uncertainty is calculated with the multi-channel analyser program followed by corrections for efficiency, branching ratio and decay time between the sampling and the measurement. Finally, the ^7Be activity is divided by the air volume to obtain the activity concentration.

5.4 Data quality control

Every acquired gamma spectrum is checked for the position and intensity of the ^{40}K gamma peak at the energy of 1460 keV.

6 Laboratory measurements of ^{210}Pb

6.1 Measurement set-up

After a six months delay period the ^{210}Pb content of the weekly filters is determined with alpha counting of the in-grown ^{210}Po using an automatic alpha/beta analyser (Figure 5, Mattsson et al. (1996)). The analyser consists of five large-area proportional counters with a steady flow of argon-methane mixture through the detectors. There are three detectors above the filter, one sensitive to alpha particles, then a beta sensitive counter and then an anticoincidence counter for background reduction. Below the filter there is one beta sensitive counter and then an anticoincidence counter for background reduction. The analyser can assay 25 samples in one measurement sequence.

Figure 5 Alpha/beta analyser Model T84 (Genera Ltd.).

6.2 Calibration and maintenance

The efficiency calibration for alpha particles has been achieved by short-lived radon progeny pseudo-coincidence counting (Mattsson et al., 1996). The detection limit of ^{210}Pb is around $20 \mu\text{Bq}/\text{m}^3$.

6.3 Data pre-processing

The software of the alpha/beta analyser calculates the net alpha count rate considering the in-growth time, in other words the disequilibrium between ^{210}Pb and ^{210}Po . The obtained net count rate is divided by alpha particle detection efficiency and the air volume to obtain the ^{210}Pb activity concentration.

6.4 Data quality control

The stability of the alpha/beta analyser is checked by weekly measurement of

- a background sample (clean Whatman GF/A filters),
- a ^{241}Am alpha reference sample, and
- a ^{90}r beta reference sample.

In addition, one actual sample, collected in Helsinki in the 1980s, is repeatedly measured once a week.

7 Total gamma radiation measurements

7.1 Measurement set-up

Gamma radiation is being measured at the ENA ARM facility since May 2015. Measurements are performed using a NaI(Tl) scintillator (Scionix, Netherlands) equipped with an electronic total count Single Channel Analyzer (SCA) counting all gamma rays in the range from 475 keV to 3 MeV.

The sampling frequency of the measurements was 15 minutes from 2015-05-07 to 2016-04-27, and 1 minute from 2016-05-04 onward. Measurements are collected from the sensor's datalogger on a weekly basis by the ENA's station staff. These raw data files are stored and preserved without modification and serve as the basis for producing pre-processed data.

7.2 Calibration and maintenance

The functionality of the sensor was tested by the manufacturer before deployment. No further maintenance is required.

The sensor is only rarely moved or disturbed, and those events are noted and considered in the quality control of the data (see below).

7.3 Data pre-processing

Data pre-processing is performed at frequencies ranging from weekly to monthly. The pre-processing procedures are implemented in the R language within a Jupyter notebook, and include:

- multiplying counts by 100, since a multiplier of 0.01 is used in the datalogger code to reduce storage needs,
- identifying gaps in the measurements, by checking if the spacing between consecutive measurements is 1 minute (or 15 minutes in the case of the earlier 15-minute measurements), and
- creating a continuous time record by filling gaps with the correct consecutive timestamps and assigning a flag (NA) for missing measurements.

After these steps, a time series plot of the pre-processed measurements is produced and visually inspected.

In case no apparent outlying values are identified by visual inspection of the time series plot, the 1-minute pre-processed data are aggregated into 15-minute time series by summing the 1-minute values. A plot of the 1-minute and 15-minute values is then produced, as the example shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Example for the year 2019: 1-minute time series of gamma radiation counts (black) and the corresponding pre-processed 15-minute series (blue).

If visual inspection of the time series plot reveals obvious issues with the pre-processed observations, specific quality-control procedures are applied before data aggregation. Examples of such cases are detailed in the following section.

7.4 Data quality control

The most common issue in the total gamma radiation measurements is related to power outages or interruptions in the instrument's power supply. When power is restored and measurements resume, the first measurement is typically incorrect (too low), as shown in Figure 7. Such outlying values are set as missing (replaced by the flag NA), as shown in Figure 8.

Only individual values are corrected in this way. Peaks and unusually high values occurring in more than one consecutive measurement are retained in the data.

Figure 7 Example of outlying gamma radiation value following a gap in the measurements.

Figure 8 Same as in Figure 2, but after quality control.

Quality control also focuses on contextual information received from the ENA station, which is used to flag potentially incorrect data. An example is shown in Figure 9 (top), where a data gap is followed by several consecutive unusual values. This coincides with field work at the station on 5 July 2017, which involved maintenance of the detector and changes to its location. In the corrected dataset, the observations from 5 July 2017 between 10:00 and 17:50 were set as missing (replaced with the NA flag), resulting in the corrected record shown in Figure 9 (bottom).

Figure 9 Illustration of quality control of total gamma radiation observations for year 2017 based on contextual station information.

Another example of quality control based on contextual information from the field site is presented in Figure 10 (top) for the year 2022. The station's technicians reported that from late May to early July there was unusual activity in the shipping container where the gamma detector is located. During this period, the sensor was moved and was not in its usual upright position for some time. Based on this information, the suspicious gamma observations from 2022-05-17 to 2022-07-18 were set to missing (replaced with the NA flag), as shown in Figure 10 (bottom).

The same quality control procedures used for the historical data are applied to the total gamma radiation data collected in the NuClim campaign.

Figure 10 Example of quality control of total gamma radiation observations for year 2022 based on contextual station information.

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